

SCAT - R/V -- AN EFFICIENT RESEARCH VESSEL FOR THE 80's AND 90's

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ABSTRACT

Proposed here is a Sailing CATamaran Research Ves-sel with a third the fuel consumption of today's research vessels. SCAT-RV has large labs, superior heavy weather gear handling ability, quiet operation under sail and a reasonably soft and level ride with her modest water plane area. Catamaran ships have been little developed because they lack bulk cargo applications. However, the very different requirements of research, coupled with greatly reduced fuel weight, make a SCAT-RV in the 130' -170' range an efficient and quiet platform for acoustic and oceanographic surveys. In the last 10 or 20 years, since the heavy displacement motor powered catamarans were designed and built, substantial advances in multi-hull naval architecture, materials and control have occurred. It is entirely feasible to build a research vessel with the speed of a clipper ship under sail; the lab space of Atlantis II; and the gear handling ability on station of LULU. TROPIC ROVER, a 150' catamaran sailing ship built for the tourist trade has demonstrated that a SCAT-RV is a practical alternative to wholesale research vessel lay ups.

INTRODUCTION - A CONTRAST IN HULL TYPES

With the dramatic rise in fuel costs in the past decade, there has been considerable interest in the return of sailing ships to oceanographic research use. Since ships like ATLANTIS, ALBATROSS, VEMA and E. B. SCRIPPS were sailing a decade or two ago, this can hardly be considered a high risk plan. Bascom et al (1981) have proposed a 1,400 ton 250' LOA and 50' beam sailing ship with roller reefed sails. The large size of this vessel was chosen to give her a reasonable hull speed of 15 knots. Not only will this hull be expensive (~\$10,000,000) but it will require a correspondingly large and expensive sail plan. A catamaran vessel with twin slender hulls will have a much higher hull speed (~40 knots) with a water line length of 130' and a length to beam ratio of 15, Edmonds (1980). Even with its greater wetted surface area per ton, the smaller, light catamaran hull form takes less power to drive at any speed, as seen in Figure 1. The dotted line is derived from model tests by Friede and Goldman (1967) for a 550 LT motor powered catamaran. The

solid curve is the estimated power vs. speed curve for a 130' SCAT-RV under power derived by reducing the weight due to fuel. Well known motor and sail powered vessels are plotted for comparison. Clearly, if half of the propulsion power is provided by sails, SCAT-RV will be fast and economical as shown by the dashed line in Figure 1. With greater righting moment and greater speed a SCAT-RV will extract more horsepower per square foot of her sail plan than a single hulled vessel. In Figure 2, Marchaj (1964) gives a polar diagram of speed made good v_s sailing on different courses divided by the wind speed v_t for two yachts. The inner circle is a ballasted monohull being driven at hull speed on all courses for gamma greater than 40°. The outer curve is the speed of a shorter unballasted catamaran with a smaller sail plan. The shaded area represents the speed difference. While it is unlikely that a research vessel will carry sufficient canvas to sail faster than the wind as in Figure 2, the difference in sailing efficiency will be substantial. Since the catamaran vessel is faster, it requires less energy per mile of cruise track to run the "hotel load" of air conditioning/heating and electric power. Crew, scientific wages and ship time are also saved by SCAT-RV's heavy weather working ability.

Figure 1: Estimated catamaran power curves.

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Figure 2: Polar plot of speed ratio V_s/V_t for a 33' catamaran and a 36' ballasted monohull.

HEELING, STABILITY AND STRUCTURE

Adverse effects of heeling are found in the efficiency of science and sailing. Since about half the time an oceanographic vessel is going to weather, heeling may be one of the major inconveniences in scientific work on a conventional sailing vessel. Heeling angles of 20° (rail buried) are common with superimposed rolling motions of 5° to 15°. As a result of such angles, the dinner table on ATLANTIS was gimballed. Stabilized lab benches might be required for much of the modern instrumentation used at sea. It may be difficult for a scientist to sleep at such angles if the vessel is tacking or coming on station repeatedly. A catamaran develops the same righting moment at 5° of heel that a typical keel boat develops at 30°. Thus a catamaran can carry the same sail area as keel boats with only 20% as much heel. Increasing the angle of heel will reduce the efficiency of any sail plan. However, it is often overlooked that this will also limit the efficiency of the centerboard or keel by limiting the aspect ratio of the keel to low values. Rudder efficiency is impaired by substantial heel angles. Bulbous bow designs which lower the resistance of tankers or freighters might not work on a heeling hull since the bulb would be displaced to one side with respect to the surface wave pattern. Because of the natural stability of large catamarans, ballast never needs to be carried. Thus, wetted surface can be reduced with further fuel savings or increased sailing speed. With high initial stability, gear can be stored almost anywhere without concern for the ship's stability. Automatic sheet release and quick furling capabilities are important on a large catamaran because she will not heel enough to spill

the wind from the sails in a truly large gust of wind thereby risking blowing out the sails. This would require expensive and time consuming repairs. The danger of capsizing catamarans is limited to smaller boats or over-canvassed racing machines (particularly those sailing in single handed races). Even relatively small cruising catamarans have excellent safety records. For example, none of James Wharram's, conservative sailing catamarans 22' to 55' long has been capsized even though hundreds of them sailed millions of miles offshore. The structure connecting the hulls of a large catamaran must be sufficiently strong to allow opposite corners of the vessel to be lifted on successive crests while the area between is unsupported in the trough. LULU clearly meets this requirement for she has been through a hurricane at sea with no adverse effect. LULU was fitted with strain gages in the critical areas for several years and no excessive strains were observed. The strength problem has been solved successfully on dozens of catamaran designs in the past twenty years. In the design suggested below, the massive box beams connecting the hulls, serve to enclose the one major lab space and one common space of 1250 ft² each.

CATAMARANS - A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The catamaran hull form is hardly a new idea. Polynesians used catamarans to make the countless epic voyages which populated all the major islands of the Pacific, long before the Europeans ventured from the protection of coastal or Mediterranean waters, Finney (1977). Catamaran ships were also popular during the early days of steam when paddle wheels could be easily protected and supported between the hulls. Fulton designed and built several twin hulled steam vessels including the U.S. Navy's first steam powered war ship. Today there are five U.S. catamaran ships in service: HAYES, WARFIELD, LULU, PIDGEON and ORTOLAN. Even though all five were first time efforts by naval architects without any previous multihull design experience, each vessel performs a number of unique tasks such as submersible tending. They also demonstrate that the structural problems of connecting two hulls have been successfully solved. All suffer defects common to first multihull design efforts including: 1) gross overweight and overloading 2) excessive water plane area 3) insufficient buoyancy forward in the bows 4) fore and aft symmetry (except Warfield) which leads to a pitching resonance. These features lead to a needlessly rough ride with high accelerations and slamming under the connecting structure in rough weather. In contrast, the oil industry uses semi-submerged catamaran vessels as drilling platforms such as the Bingo 3000 class. These vessels have minimum water plane area when submerged for drilling and are propelled between drilling sites as regular catamarans with less wetted surface and thus lower drag. The Japanese firm Mitsui has built a semi-submerged high speed ferry which is in regular passenger service. Here passenger comfort at high speed is traded for increased wetted surface and thus increased fuel use. While semi-sub-

Figure 3: TROPIC ROVER - 150' LOA + 20' Bowsprit, 125' LWL, 40' beam, 8 1/2' draft & 275 LT displacement loaded. (56 passengers and 18 crew including 3 officers, 1 engineer, 2 cooks, 3 ABs & 9 stewards).

merged designs optimize comfort, they seriously compromise the restoring moment needed to carry sails and add greater draft and complexity of operation. It is interesting to note that all of the successful sailing catamarans designed for cruising have a water plane area intermediate between the semi-submersible and that of the five existing large motor powered catamarans.

THE EXAMPLE OF TROPIC ROVER

TROPIC ROVER was designed and built by Capt. Sidney Hartshorn (1981) for the tourist trade in the Bahamas. Unlike the five catamarans above, she was the second catamaran built by Hartshorne (the first being 70' TROPIC BIRD) with advice from the foremost catamaran experts of the day, principally the post war Hawaiian designers. Her 6 1/2' hull beam at the water line gave her a small water plane area and hence a soft enough ride to be very comfortable for the 56 inexperienced tourists she carried. Figure 3 clearly

shows the substantial buoyancy carried in her bows. In all the years she was sailed weekly across the Gulf Stream, her crossings were never delayed due to bad weather. During the worst northerly blows against the Gulf Stream, she never slammed or creaked due to her buoyancy forward and her massive box beams connecting the hulls. However, green water would occasionally pass over the bow of the lee hull on a reach in heavy weather. Since the bottom and sides of each hull were flat joined by sharp corners, the hull was optimized for economy of construction out of plywood (1" sides and 2" bottoms) rather than speed. Her sails were made of cotton of marginal strength and thus could not be sheeted in hard for maximum speed. Even so, she could easily go 13 to 16 knots on a reach under sail alone. With a total of 280 hp she was grossly under powered for a ship of her windage. While beating, the 140 hp engine in the lee hull was often run by Hartshorne "to act as a centerboard" increasing Tropic Rover's windward efficiency. Her unique features included

twin landing craft which could put the entire group of 56 tourists on a beach or be used to explore regions too shallow for Rover's 8 1/2' draft. As a research vessel her compliment would have been cut in half giving room for 28 scientists and 9 crew. Her sails were handled exclusively on the top deck with other activities confined to the deck below which was the interior of the massive box beams. This minimizes the conflict between rigging and other activity which was a common problem on the old sailing research vessels. Capt. Hartshorn who has commanded a number of research vessels including HERO, CALANUS and ISELIN as well as sailing vessels, believes that a large catamaran sailing ship would be the ideal research platform for most applications.

A STRAWMAN LAYOUT FOR A 170' SCAT-RV

The overall size of the SCAT-RV was chosen so that the interior of the box beams connecting the hulls and the interiors of the hulls themselves can be used for lab, stateroom, galley, machinery and storage spaces. As seen in Figure 4, the ship has five levels. The top level is the sail handling and bridge deck. With the price of solar voltaic cells predicted to fall by a factor of 10 in the next five years, the top deck could be paved with large arrays. This will provide quiet electric power free from voltage transients and it will reduce the temptation of the ship user to overload SCAT-RV by adding equipment topside. This arrangement gives the bridge a completely unobstructed

view of all points including the recessed working deck below and the center well. The upper level has lab spaces, working deck and common areas located in the hulls and the box beams. Winches are located on the working deck under the overhanging top of the elliptical hull sections. A traveling overhead crane spanning the working deck would be able to move loads anywhere on deck, service winches, lift engines up through hatches from below and support fairlead blocks to lower gear through the well near the pitch and roll center of the ship. Such a crane would not interfere with the sails above and would not have a failure prone azimuthal drive mechanism which is loaded periodically by ship motion. Vans with special lab equipment or extra scientific accommodations could be located on the working deck with protection from boarding seas and have air lock access to the air-conditioned labs rather than the humid decks. The middle level contains 8-12' x 12' staterooms in each hull at the major axis of the elliptical hull crosssection with a shared head and access ladder between rooms. The lower level contains water and fuel tanks which are small owing to her fuel efficiency. Major bulkheads within the box beams would be continued down to the keel in each hull to tie the entire structure together.

STATION KEEPING AND GEAR HANDLING IN HEAVY WEATHER

The distance between the twin propellers of the 170' catamaran discussed here is over 40', giving it a large turning moment by putting one engine ahead and one astern. In rough weather a catamaran with high freeboard aft, can put her sterns

into the wind and waves pulling herself to windward under power from two widely separated propellers. This is a stabilizing process, whereas, pushing a vessel to windward is a destabilizing process which requires a bow thruster to keep the ship's head up. The working deck is ten feet above the full-load water line and thus would be rather dry in rough weather with protection behind the aft box beam and bridge. Green water on deck would be a problem only when the trough-to-crest height of the significant waves approaches 20 feet. This corresponds to a whole gale with sea state 6 or Beaufort 9 sea conditions. The working deck surrounding the well should be expanded metal grating for good footing and instant drainage. Small instruments like CTDs, BTs or hydrophones could be lowered through the lab floor on the center line of the ship without going on deck. The ship is so arranged that it is unnecessary to go out on exposed decks in heavy weather except to repair the automatic sail trimming gear.

With 30' between the hulls and restraining lines on all sides of a load, the usual pendulous motion of instruments can be easily controlled, particularly if the loads are supported at the pitch and roll center of the ship in the center of the well. To further reduce motion on station, a small riding sail could be carried roller furled, between stations ahead of the foremast. With precision navigation such as High Fix, GPS or sea bottom mounted acoustic transponder arrays, dynamic positioning could be achieved using variable pitch propellers and computer control. Bow thrusters would be needed only to dock in tight quarters in strong winds. SCAT-RV has considerable windage and thus requires substantial reserve power. With limited space in the hulls and variable demands, it would be convenient to divide the power plant into four to six modules. If these were skid mounted, diesel hydraulic units with quick disconnect fittings, the proper amount of power would be available at peak efficiency and maintenance

LOA - 170' + 30' bowsprit
 LWL - 160'
 Hull beam @ water line - 10'
 Hull beam @ middle level - 12'
 Extreme Beam - 54'
 Draft full load - 9'
 Full load displacement - 475 LT
 Light load displacement - 375 LT
 Wing clearance - 10'
 Distance between hulls - 30'
 Mast height - 135'

Figure 4a: Hypothetical layout for SCAT-RV (front)

Figure 4b: Hypothetical layout for SCAT-RV (top). Note the 2050 ft² recessed working deck, 450 ft² well, 1250 ft² forward lab, 1250 ft² common space, 750 ft² bridge.

Figure 4c: Hypothetical layout for SCAT-RV (side). Note the 2500 ft² living spaces in the hulls, 2000 ft² machinery and storage space and twin masted fore and aft roller reefed sails.

would be simple. Hydraulic drive will prevent engine damage from overspeeding if a propellor comes out of the water under load in heavy weather. Hydraulic motors will be used for winches, sail trimming, anchor windlasses and crane power due to their compact size, light weight and easy maintenance.

MISSIONS POORLY SUITED TO CATAMARANS

Large catamarans are poorly suited to several missions undertaken in oceanography. The most impractical mission is polar oceanography where a vessel encounters floating ice. Large chunks of ice can wedge between the hulls and cause large drag such as occurred with Fulton's Hudson River ferries. It would be impractical to ice-strengthen the hulls or the connecting structures. The use of catamarans for bulk freight or heavy tank-

age loads is impractical because the increased displacement of the vessel would erase the performance advantages of catamarans. This lack of practical use as a bulk carrier is, I believe, the main reason why relatively little development effort has been put into large twin hulled vessels. It further argues that a sailing catamaran will be more practical as a research vessel than a catamaran exclusively relying on motor propulsion, since a motor vessel would need a much larger weight of fuel.

EXAMPLES OF MISSIONS UNIQUELY SUITED TO CATAMARANS

It is generally agreed that the catamaran R/V LULU is the most successful submersible tender in the world. LULU and ALVIN have logged more than 1,000 dives in the last 15 years. LULU is able to work in higher sea states and with greater safety than

any other submersible tender. Although the R/V KNORR was fitted with a special heavy duty articulated crane designed to lift ALVIN, this crane remains on the WHOI dock. Other submersibles are tended from a variety of barges or less stable vessels. One exception is the DSRV which is tended from the 251' catamaran vessels PIDGEON and ORTOLAN. LULU has also been used successfully to launch and recover the underwater habitat, EDLHAB. LULU or another large catamaran would also be an ideal platform for the operation of lock-out saturation diving gear or RCV's. A large catamaran sailing research vessel would make a logical replacement for the aging and overcrowded LULU. It could be easily fitted with LULU's elevator system and carry all the van and other support equipment. Since ALVIN is operating routinely over the mid-ocean ridges far from home, the cost of towing ships to work with LULU would be eliminated. During ALVIN's overhaul periods, SCAT-RV could be used for other research projects. Catamarans are well suited for modest drilling operations or deep coring work. Tubes about 100' long could be lifted by topping lifts between the 135' masts and restrained from swinging. With its light weight and great structural strength, a catamaran could even be jacked up in shallow water for bottom maintenance, and scientific work such as drilling or observations in the surf zone or coral reefs. Missions where delicate work with minimum heeling and acceleration tolerance are well suited to catamarans. Short student cruises with large numbers of inexperienced people would be carried out with minimum sea sickness problems. Nearshore work would be ideally suited to catamarans with shoal draft. Catamarans would be well suited to working in their ancestral waters of the mid Pacific or other regions where fuel and supporting facilities are scarce and expensive. There, the speed and extended range of SCAT-RV would be welcome.

Missions where large amounts of equipment need to be loaded or unloaded from an undeveloped region where beach or shallow harbor loading is required, could be handled relatively easily by carrying a small aluminum landing craft which would be hoisted through the well to working deck levels for easy loading and unloading and could be driven up to the beach.

The redundancy, repairability and portability of propulsion gear would be helpful in remote locations. Multidisciplinary scientific studies such as CUEA, where large numbers of investigators and technicians need to work together to assure simultaneous collocated data are natural catamaran applications. Aerial surveys with underway mapping can be laid out to take advantage of the catamaran's sailing speed on a beam reach.

CONCLUSIONS

A large sailing catamaran research vessel is practical today. A 375 LT catamaran could operate at 10 knots under power using 1/3 of the 800 hp used by our new coastal zone research vessels to go 11 knots. With a proper sail plan, these savings could be increased from 2/3 to about 5/6 of present fuel consumption. At this level of consumption, oceanographic research, from such deep sea

ships could continue into the next century in the face of possible severe oil shortages. Our recent attempts to cut fuel usage by building smaller conventional ships has very definite limits. We are faced with need for oceanographic vessels with flexibility and sea keeping ability of a 1400 ton vessel but with the fuel and construction savings of a 400 ton vessel. I think a sailing catamaran research vessel uniquely fits these seemingly contradictory requirements. With rising fuel costs laying up the academic and government research fleets, it is time to take strong action if we wish to have a significant seagoing research fleet in the 80's, 90's and beyond. While remote sensing is sure to play an ever-expanding role in oceanography, I find it difficult to believe that seagoing work will be replaced for subsurface measurements by remote sensing. We should not be lulled into a nostalgic trap of believing we can go back to the days of pre-WWII oceanography under sail. The scientific gear being handled today such as massive moorings, submersibles, large core samples or fishing nets and deep towed devices would be difficult to handle from traditional sailing vessels.

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